

EAGER: LEVERAGING ADVANCED CYBERINFRASTRUCTURE AND DEVELOPING ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE FOR NSF MAJOR FACILITIES IN THE PANDEMIC ERA

Project Overview & Preliminary Findings

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MEET THE RESEARCH TEAM

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PROJECT OVERVIEW

Among major workplaces disrupted by the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic are NSF major facilities (MFs), an important part of US scientific communities. MFs are also utilizing and developing advanced cyberinfrastructure (CI) to support their science missions. CI represents a key factor in MF's planning for and adapting to disruptive events.

In this study, we explore how to design MF organizations to be resilient to future crises and major disasters and to inform future CI innovations that can support the MFs' science missions during major disruptions.

The synergistic and integrative model we will develop can provide a framework for MFs and other projects, teams, and organizations in the broader NSF science community to prepare for and adapt to future major crises. The outcome will be to minimize negative impacts and maintain the continuity of the scientific efforts in times of crisis.

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

Pandemic Response Strategies

1. Promote Flexible Expectations at Work

Adapting aims and expectations, such as embracing remote work, can lead to the ability to manage crises more successfully, as well as discovering more efficient systems of operations.

2. Encourage Information Sharing in the Community and the Ecosystem

Shared knowledge can offer guidance for risk management practices as well as offering a sense of community with other MFs, research teams, and institutions during a crisis. In addition, to self-organize following a crisis, individuals must know their roles and chain of command.

3. Create Optimal Alignments Across Institutions (including Funders)

While too many institutional requirements can cause confusion, institutional guidance is essential to MF crisis response, as institutions offer stability, a sense of finality in decisions, normalcy, and, at times, a durable scapegoat for pandemic frustrations.

4. Sensitize Team to Risk to Balance Safety and Productivity

Sensitizing teams to the pandemic can reduce underestimating and/or overestimating the risks associated with the crisis by both workers and management in their response efforts.

5. Keep Work Going Despite Pandemic Challenges

Because the practice of doing scientific research gives meaning to involved workers, keeping work going despite challenges aids in team functioning and morale.

Pandemic-Sensitized Mindset

6. Know Your Vulnerabilities

Rather than attempting to pre-emptively identify all vulnerabilities, developing a knowledge base surrounding general areas of vulnerability and strategies for reacting can aid crisis response.

7. Acknowledge that No Science is an Island

The pandemic further exposed the reality that scientific research projects are impacted by social, institutional, and political forces—that scientific research cannot be separated from world events.

8. Look for Socio-Technical (not just Technical) Solutions

Solutions cannot be evaluated solely on a technical level—rather, a human-centered approach needs to be put in place. Technologies may be useful, but tools that are already utilized within teams were more successful than creating or adopting new solutions.

9. Integrate the Personal and Professional

The crisis displayed that teams must consider the human needs of workers and researchers involved to minimize burnout, as boundaries between professional work environments and personal life blurred.

10. Cultivate Readiness to Adapt in the New Normal

Waiting for “the new normal” hindered teams, as participants described situations of inability to adapt to changing circumstances due to hoping instead for a return to a status quo. Given the understanding that crises and pandemics will happen again, working in a relative “pandemic-ready” mode and regard it as the new normal may be preemptively wise.

